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Carriedo, N., Corral, A., Montoro, P. R., Herrero, L., & Rucían, M. (2016). Development of the updating executive function: From 7-year-olds to young adults. *Developmental psychology*, 52(4), 666–678.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000091>

Title: Development of the updating executive function: from 7-year-olds to young adults

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Abstract

Updating information in working memory (WM) is a critical executive function responsible both for continuously replacing outdated information with new relevant data and to suppress or inhibit content that is no longer relevant according to task demands. The goal of the present research is twofold: First, we aimed to study updating development in 548 participants of 4 different age ranges—7-, 11-, and 15-year-olds and young adults— using the updating task devised by R. De Beni and P. Palladino (2004), which allows differentiating maintenance and inhibition processes. Second, we attempted to determine the relation between these processes across development as well as the differentiation among different types of inhibition processes tapped by this task. Results showed that there was an improvement of memory performance with age along with an upgrading of inhibitory efficiency. However, whereas in memory performance, a progressive increase was observed until the age of 15 years followed by stabilization, in inhibition, a continuous progressive increase was observed until young adulthood. Importantly, results showed that development of the different inhibitory mechanisms does not progress equally. All the groups committed more errors related to inefficient suppression mechanisms in WM than errors related to control of long-term memory interference. Principal component analysis showed that updating implies different subprocesses: active maintenance/suppression of information in WM and control of proactive interference. Developmental trajectories showed that the maintenance/suppression of information in the WM component continues to develop far beyond adolescence but that proactive interference control is responsible for variations in updating across development.

Keywords: updating information in Working Memory, inhibitory processes, cognitive development.

Updating information in working memory (WM) has been identified—together with inhibition and shifting—as one of the three independent but related executive functions, both in adults (Miyake et al., 2000) and in children and adolescents (Huizinga, Dolan, & van der Molen, 2006; Lehto, Juujärvi, Kooistra, & Pulkkinen, 2003; Xu et al., 2013). Updating has been defined as “*the act of modifying the current status of representation of schema in memory to accommodate new input*” (Morris & Jones, 1990, p.112). This definition implies the ability to replace current content in WM with new content, but also to suppress or inhibit content that is no longer relevant as a function of task demands. The importance of updating has been underlined not only because it is extremely relevant for everyday life, where we must continuously replace old information with new relevant data, but also because it is a significant predictor of high cognitive abilities such as fluid intelligence (Yntema & Mueser, 1962), academic achievement (Gathercole, Pickering, Knight, & Stegmann, 2004) and higher mental abilities such as reasoning (Barrouillet, 1996; Barrouillet & Lecas, 1999; Kyllonen & Christal, 1990) and reading comprehension (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980; Daneman & Merikle, 1996; Just & Carpenter, 1992; Swanson & Berninger, 1995).

Processes underlying updating information in WM

Due to the high correlations found between updating measures and WM tasks (Conway, 1996; Engle, Tuholski, Laughlin, & Conway, 1999; Lehto, 1996; Miyake et al., 2000; Schmiedek, Hildebrandt, Lövdén, Wilhelm, and Lindenberger, 2009; St Clair-Thompson & Gathercole, 2006; Towse, Hitch, & Hutton, 1998), it has been considered that WM updating tasks (e.g., n-back, keep-track, or running memory tasks) and WM span tasks (e.g., Reading Span Task-RST- by Daneman & Carpenter, 1980) could be used indistinctively and interchangeably because they are measuring the same construct (e.g., Schmiedek, et al., 2009). However, other authors (e.g., Ecker, Lewandowsky & Oberauer, 2014) concluded that updating and WM must be conceptually and theoretically differentiated because otherwise, there would be no empirical basis to postulate updating as a separate executive function.

Thus, to avoid a redundant construct, processes underlying updating must be isolated and measured separately from other WM processes.

In this line, Bledowski, Kaiser, and Rahm (2010), following WM models by Cowan (1988) and Oberauer (2002), identified five control mechanisms in WM: a) Selection of information; b) Focus updating; c) Content updating; d) Rehearsal; e) Coping with interference. Bledowski et al. (2010) also stated that content updating may only be partially related to Miyake et al.'s (2000) updating executive function, which may rely to a much greater degree on the monitoring and manipulation of information in WM, and which necessarily implies encoding and inhibiting information.

Ecker, Lewandowsky, Oberauer & Chee, (2010) differentiated three independent potential subprocesses in updating: retrieval, transformation and substitution, finding that performance in updating tasks could largely be explained in terms of transformation and retrieval, and to a lesser extent, in terms of a substitution process. Moreover, when comparing updating tasks to complex WM Span Tasks, these authors concluded that “*substitution was the only process that unequivocally contributes variance that is unique to Working memory updating*” (Ecker et al., 2010, p. 18).

Kessler and Meiran (2008) made another proposal, identifying at least two subprocesses in updating: (a) the modification of WM content of relevant items and the preservation of the content of the other items (local updating) and (b) the inhibition or protection against interference of WM contents (global updating). Recently, Kessler and Oberauer (2014) argued that updating and maintenance require two different states (modes of operation) of WM, and that the variance of the updating performance was explained by the cost of shifting between updating and maintenance.

Therefore, manipulation of information (monitoring or transforming incoming information), maintenance, and inhibition (suppression of irrelevant information and coping with interference) seem to be the key processes in updating WM content. A question of

interest is to determine the extent to which these updating subprocesses are related and whether this relationship varies across development.

Development of updating executive function

Most of the developmental studies of updating executive function were carried out considering updating and WM as if they were the same construct (see Best & Miller, 2010, for a review). These studies, using complex WM span tasks, usually reported a continued high development of WM from late childhood to adolescence followed by a plateau between late adolescence and early adulthood (e.g., Gathercole et al., 2004), a profile which is similar to the development of synaptic pruning in prefrontal cortex as a function of age (Huttenlocher, 1990). However, other frequently cited studies also reported continued development of WM during adolescence to young adulthood (Luna, Garver, Urban, Lazar, & Sweeney, 2004). These apparently contradictory results could be due to the diversity of tasks used in the different studies that could not tap exactly the same processes.

In order to address this issue, Luciana, Conklin, Hooper, and Yarger (2005) used different WM spatial tasks that varied in the degree to which they required executive control, suggesting that WM develops in a dimensional hierarchical manner. When the task requires high executive control, development continues up to the age of 16 years and remains stable around 18 to 20 years. On the contrary, when the task only requires low memory demands, development remains stable from 11 to 12 years of age (see also Conklin, Luciana, Hooper, & Yarger, 2007, and Luciana et al., 2005, for a similar account). However, these studies have focused on the development of updating using complex WM span tasks that did not take into account that not only maintenance but also inhibition is a key component of the updating process.

There are few developmental studies that address the issue of the relationship between maintenance and inhibitory processes implied in WM tasks. Robert, Borella, Fagot, Lecerf, and De Ribaupierre (2009) carried out a study to examine the extent to which inhibitory control and WM capacity are related across the life span with a group of children aged 11 years and three groups of adults (young adults, old adults, and very old adults). Studying

inhibitory processes in the Reading Span Test while manipulating memory load (maintenance), they found that the rate of intrusions—an index of inhibitory efficiency—increased as memory load increased; however, they did not find age differences in memory load costs. In contrast, Loosli, Rahm, Unterrainer, Weiller, and Kaller (2014) failed to find developmental differences in proactive interference in n-back task, a classical updating task. The absence of differences in inhibitory processes in n-back task could raise some doubts about the contribution of inhibitory processes to updating, but some authors (Carretti, Cornoldi, De Beni, & Romanò, 2005; Palladino, Cornoldi, De Beni, & Pazzaglia, 2001; Ruiz, Elosúa, & Lechuga, 2005) maintain that classical updating tasks do not necessarily require updating, because participants could adopt the passive strategy of waiting until the last items to recall them using a recency criterion. Thus, performance in this kind of tasks could be due to passive maintenance mechanisms and not to the updating executive function (Ruiz et al., 2005) that implies, as mentioned, not only maintenance processes, but also transformation of incoming information and inhibition: suppressing irrelevant information and coping with interference.

The present study

Our goal is to study updating executive function development using the updating task devised by De Beni and Palladino (2004; Palladino et al., 2001), which allows differentiating maintenance and inhibition processes. Moreover, we aimed to empirically test the relation/independence of these processes across development as well as the differentiation made by these authors among different types of inhibition processes tapped by this task. As Robert et al. (2009) pointed out, the study of the relationship between maintenance and inhibition also has important theoretical implications. The inhibitory deficit theory postulates that Working Memory capacity (WMC) is determined mainly by the efficiency of inhibitory processes. That is, inhibition drives WMC (Bjorklund & Harnishfeger, 1995; Dempster, 1992; Harnishfeger, 1995; Hasher & Zacks, 1988; Hasher, Lusting & Zacks, 2007). On the contrary, other authors postulate that executive attention drives inhibitory efficiency (Engle,

2002). That is, individual differences in inhibition—and perhaps developmental differences— could be the result of limitations in WMC, which constrains the availability of resources required for inhibition.

The updating task devised by Palladino and colleagues (see De Beni & Palladino, 2004; Palladino et al., 2001) allows differentiating these two components of the updating process —maintenance and inhibition—, posing variable demands on memory load and suppression, and it also permits the study of the interaction of both processes. Importantly, this task also taxes different inhibition/interference processes (suppression of information in WM and proactive interference) providing different indexes of them. In this task, participants listen to lists of concrete and abstract words and are asked to recall a variable number of these according to a semantic criterion (i.e., the smallest items presented, objects, or animals). Thus, during the task, participants have to process each piece of incoming information, maintaining it actively in WM and inhibiting items that are no longer relevant. Compared to the classical reaction time updating tasks (n-back, keep-track, or running memory) —which only require retrieval and substitution (not transformation)— this task has some advantages: First, it includes the three components identified by Ecker et al. (2010): (a) a comparison component: participants had to consider each item included on the list, comparing each new item with those maintained in memory; (b) a substitution component: items no longer relevant (larger items) have to be substituted by the new smaller ones; and (c) a retrieval component: participants have to maintain in memory and then recall the smallest items. Moreover, this task requires selecting items on the basis of a relevance criterion, not only having to recall the last items, like in classical memory updating tasks (see for a similar account Carretti, Cornoldi, & Pelegrina, 2007). This task has proved to be able to detect individual differences in high order cognitive abilities such as reading comprehension (Carretti et al., 2005; Palladino et al., 2001) or word problem solving (Passolunghi & Pazzaglia, 2005). Furthermore, this updating task— compared to other WM tasks that demand less attentional control—proved to be the task with the greatest power to discriminate between typical developing children and children with intellectual disability

(ID) even when controlling for fluid intelligence (Carretti, Bellacchi, & Cornoldi, 2010). In addition, it is also sensitive to developmental and aging changes (De Beni & Palladino, 2004; Lechuga, Moreno, Pelegrina, Gómez-Ariza, & Bajo, 2006).

In the developmental arena, Lechuga et al. (2006) used this task to explore the development of intentional cognitive inhibition in children, adolescents, and young adults, aged 8, 11, and 18 years old. They found recall and intrusion (an index of inhibition difficulties) differences between 8-year-olds and 11-year-olds, and between 8-year-olds and 18-year-olds, but not between 11-year-olds and 18-year-olds. Moreover, a significant effect of memory load was found at all ages, but the effect of level of suppression was only significant at the age of 8 for recall of critical items and at ages 8 and 11 for intrusions. Based on these results, these authors concluded that there is an improvement of inhibitory processes as age increases. As in De Beni and Palladino's study, Lechuga et al. (2006) also found a relative independence between maintenance and inhibition processes tapped by this task.

The results obtained by Lechuga et al. (2006) seem to replicate the studies that claim that updating develops until adolescence and to contradict those that state that updating continues to develop through adolescence into adulthood. However, despite its undisputable contribution, this study could have some potential limitations: First, the sample was too small; Second, the age divisions made did not allow exploring development throughout adolescence: the study may lack a group of 14-15-year-old adolescents between the 11-year-olds and the young adults. Finally, because they reached conclusions about the development of cognitive inhibition as if it were a unitary construct, based on intrusions taken as a whole, but they did not study the development of the different kind of intrusions—which reflect different types of inhibition/interference processes (De Beni & Palladino, 2004)—so that they could follow different development patterns.

The present study tried to overcome these potential limitations. First, we aimed to extend the results obtained by Lechuga et al. (2006) to a much broader sample of participants ($n = 548$) of age ranges more sensitive to developmental changes in executive functioning —

7-, 11-, and 15-year-olds and young adults— in order to analyze developmental changes both in memory maintenance (recall accuracy) and in inhibition (intrusions). In order to analyze different sources of inhibitory/interference processes, we followed the differentiation performed by De Beni and Palladino, (2004) among: (a) same-list intrusions, related to suppression mechanisms that control activation/suppression of information in WM; (b) previous-list intrusions, related to the control of proactive interference in long-term memory (LTM); and (c) inventions, recall of items never presented, related to the control of intrusive irrelevant thoughts coming from LTM. Related to this first objective, and according to previous studies, we expected continuous and progressive developmental changes both in recall accuracy and inhibition, especially in more demanding conditions, both with regard to memory maintenance (high load condition) and to inhibition (high suppression condition). A second aim of the present study was to explore the relationship between maintenance and inhibition processes in updating information in WM across development, specifically:

1. The relative independence found in previous studies (De Beni & Palladino, 2004; Lechuga et al., 2006) between maintenance and inhibition processes in WM as well as the different contribution of each one of these processes to updating information. If maintenance and inhibition are related, we would expect a significant Load x Suppression interaction. Moreover, if this interaction changes across development, then a significant Age x Load x Suppression interaction would also be expected. Additionally, if—according to inhibitory deficit theory— inhibition drives WM capacity, developmental differences in inhibition would not depend on memory load. On the contrary, if—according to executive attention theory—individual differences in inhibition could be the result of limitations in WM capacity, then suppression would be less likely to occur when memory demands increase. Moreover, if both processes are related, we would expect them to load on the same component in principal component analysis (PCA), or even if they load on different components, these components should correlate with each other.

2. The hypothetical differentiation among the different types of inhibition/interference processes and their different contribution to efficient updating. If the different intrusions indexes tap different inhibition processes, we would expect them to load on different components and that their developmental trajectories would also be different.

Method

The data presented here were collected as part of a larger, multifaceted study. Individuals participated in four separate sessions, lasting 4 to 8 weeks in children and adolescents, and 4 days in adults. Children and adolescents completed 12 different executive tasks and other psychometric tests to measure fluid intelligence, reading comprehension, and academic aptitudes. Adults performed 3 executive tasks, fluid intelligence, and other paper and pencil tasks. The order of tasks was counterbalanced in all age groups. Data from these participants have not been used in other articles.

Participants

The sample for this study consisted of 548 volunteer students. Their distribution by ages was as follows: 150 seven-year-old children (75 girls and 75 boys; age range 7.2-8.3, $M = 7.3$, $SD = .42$); 150 eleven-year-old children (77 girls and 73 boys; range 10.10-12.3, $M = 11$, $SD = .40$); 150 fifteen-year-olds (84 girls and 66 boys; range 14.11-16.1, $M = 15$, $SD = .40$); and 98 young adults (51 women and 57 men, range 20-35, $M = 15$, $SD = 2.18$). Children were recruited from seven middle-class primary and secondary schools. Adults were university students recruited from different universities.

Design

We used a mixed factorial 4 x (2x2) design with age as between-subject factor and memory load (low and high) and suppression (low and high) as within-subject factors. Memory load was the measured number of items by size to be recalled (3 in the low load condition or 5 in the high load condition). Suppression was the number of potential target words that had to be

discarded from the selected group of words because they no longer represented the smallest objects (2 in the low suppression condition or 5 in the high suppression condition). Dependent variables were the percentage of correctly recalled words, and the percentage of intrusions (incorrectly recalled words) as an inhibition index. Following De Beni and Palladino (2004), we differentiated three types of intrusions: (a) same-list intrusions that could be linked to the suppression of information in WM; (b) previous-list intrusions related to proactive interference; and (c) and inventions, associated with the control of intrusive irrelevant thoughts coming from LTM.

Materials

We used an updating task devised by De Beni and Palladino (2004; Palladino et al., 2001) and adapted by (Lechuga et al., 2006). The task was composed of 24 lists (20 experimental and 4 practice lists) of 12 words each. Each list included words to be recalled (relevant words), words to be discarded (irrelevant words), and filler words. The number of each kind of word in each list varied depending on the experimental condition. Thus, the number of relevant words in each list varied between 3 (low memory load) and 5 (high memory load). The number of irrelevant words varied between 2 (low suppression) and 5 (high suppression). Finally, the number of abstract filler words varied from 2 to 7. The composition of lists as a function of memory load and suppression can be seen in Table 1.

[Insert Table 1 here]

Target words (relevant and irrelevant) were familiar concrete nouns, which referred to body parts, objects, or animals that can be classified by size. Filler words were abstract nouns. From the 288 words included in the task, 194 were taken from Lechuga et al. (2006). The remaining 94 words were frequent words extracted from Justicia (1995). Word frequency, concreteness, and familiarity were controlled using “*BuscaPalabras*”[SearchWords] software (Davis & Perea, 2005). Moreover, words were assigned to lists controlling that the words on each list were clearly discriminable by size and their phonetic similarity was low. Additionally, we carried out a previous study with 30 children —aged between 7 and 16

years—and 10 adults in order to verify that all the selected words were understood by participants, were easily identified as concrete or abstract, and were discriminable as a function of size. A word was finally included only when it was selected by more than 90% of the participants, which met the criteria used both by De Beni and Palladino (2004) and by Lechuga et al. (2006).

We finally included 288 frequent ($M = 57$ per million, $SD = 99$) and familiar ($M = 5.97$, $SD = .71$ on a 7-point scale) words. Of them, 108 were abstract words and 180 concrete words. Abstract words had a mean concreteness value of 3.44 ($SD = .62$ on a 7-point scale) whereas concrete words had a mean concreteness value of 6.04 ($SD = .43$ on a 7-point scale).

The final 24 lists were distributed in 4 experimental conditions of 6 lists. One list of each experimental condition was considered as practice list. Thus, each experimental condition was composed of 5 lists. The total words to be recalled across all condition lists were 80 (practice lists were excluded), 25 in the case of each high load condition and 15 in the case of each low load condition. In 10 of the lists, the participants were asked to remember the 3 smallest items (low load condition), whereas in the remaining 10 lists, they had to remember the 5 smallest items (high load condition). Likewise, in 10 of the lists, participants had to suppress the previously presented items that were no longer the smallest items: 2 items for the 10 lists included in the low suppression condition and 5 items for the 10 lists included in the high suppression condition (see Table 1).

An example list of high memory load and low inhibition was: acción (action), avión (airplane), cuchillo (knife), esperanza (hope), estuche (pencil case), honor (honor), lengua (tongue), manzana (apple), mezcla (mixture), mesa (table), uña (fingernail), verdad (truth). Of these 12 words, participants had to recall the 5 smallest items (knife, pencil case, tongue, apple, fingernail) and to inhibit 2 words (airplane, table).

Procedure

All the participants were tested individually and they performed two tasks: an updating task and a delayed recall task. For the updating task, twenty-four lists, each comprising twelve

auditory words, were presented to participants. Within each list, the auditory stimuli lasted less than 1000 ms and were presented at a constant speed with a 2-s interval between words. Presentation order of the lists was randomized and, additionally, within each list, item presentation was also randomized. Randomization and time were controlled by E-Prime software, version 2.0 (Psychology Software Tools Inc; www.pst-net.com/eprime).

The experiment started with the updating task –consisting of a practice phase of four lists and an experimental updating phase of twenty lists– followed by an interpolating task (backwards counting task) and then, by a delayed recall task (only the results for the updating task are presented in this paper). In the updating task, participants were instructed to carefully listen to the list and when it finished, they had to recall the 3 or 5 smallest animals or objects on the list. At the beginning of each list, a text message was displayed on a computer screen to indicate the concrete number of smallest items to remember (3 or 5). Then, a beep preceded the first word of the list. At the end of each list of 12 items, a different beep and a big question mark on the screen asked the participants to recall the 3 or 5 smallest items of the current list by verbal response. To continue with the next list, participants had to press the space bar. Thus, during the task, participants had to update words according to a semantic criteria (size) that implies substituting and inhibiting previously presented words that are no longer relevant under variable conditions of maintenance (words to be recalled) and inhibition (words to be discarded or inhibited).

Results

Participants' performance was analyzed in terms of proportion of recall of relevant items (as updating index) and proportion of intrusions (as inhibition index). Proportion of recall of relevant items and proportion of all the intrusion types were calculated over the total number of words to be recalled. It should be borne in mind that, depending on the experimental condition, the number of words to be recalled varied: 25 for the high memory load conditions and 15 for the low memory load conditions. The proportion of missing answers was calculated by subtracting the total number of words recalled + inventions + intrusions from the total

number of words to be recalled, and dividing it by 25 (high load conditions) or by 15 (low load conditions).

A mixed 4x (2 x2) ANOVA was performed with age as between-subject factor, and memory load (high and low) and level of suppression (high and low) as within-subject factors for the all the dependent variables. Only main results are presented. Bonferroni correction was applied in multiple comparisons.

Proportion of recall of critical items

Table 2 (panel A) shows the mean proportion of recall in each one of the experimental conditions for each age group. Statistical analysis showed a significant effect of age, $F(3, 544) = 105.24, p < .001, \eta^2 = .37$. Multiple comparisons showed differences between 7-, 11- and 15-year-olds (all $ps < .001$), but the recall of critical words was similar for 15-year-olds and young adults. We also found a significant interaction Memory Load x Age, $F(3, 544) = 3.84, p < .01, \eta^2 = .02$, revealing that load differences were significant for all ages, and that those differences were higher for the younger children: 7 and 11 year-olds.

[Insert Table 2]

There was also a significant Age x Load x Suppression interaction, $F(3, 544) = 7.79, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. That is, under low load condition differences between levels of suppression were significant for 7-year-olds, $t(544) = -6.04, p < .00001, \eta^2 = .06$; 11-year-olds, $t(544) = -4.95, p < .0001, \eta^2 = .04$; and 15-year-olds, $t(544) = -3.38, p < .002, \eta^2 = .02$, but not for young adults. On the other hand, under high memory load, the effect of suppression was not the same for all the age groups: a) it was significant for 7-year-olds, $t(544) = -2.22, p < .03, \eta^2 = .01$, but in the opposite direction to the predicted one: these children recalled fewer words in the low suppression condition than in the high suppression condition; b) it was significant in the in the predicted direction for 15-year-olds, $t(544) = 2.007, p < .05, \eta^2 = .01$; c) it was not significant either for 11-year-olds or for young adults. Moreover, differences between high and low memory load were significant both under high suppression and low suppression for all the ages, but for 15-year-olds, the direction

was contrary to that expected (all $ps < .0001$).

[Insert Figure 1]

Proportion of Intrusions.

Intrusions are errors referring to words recalled that are not the target words. Proportion of intrusions was calculated by dividing the errors by the total number of words to be recalled for each experimental condition (see Table 2, panel B). Statistical analyses showed a significant main effect of age, $F(3, 544) = 33.36, p < .001, \eta^2 = .16$. Multiple comparisons showed differences between every age group (7 year-olds > 11 year-olds > 15 year-olds > young adults (all $ps < .05$). There was also a significant Age x Load interaction, $F(3, 544) = 18.8, p < .001, \eta^2 = .10$. The analysis of this interaction showed that the high memory load produced an increment of errors at all ages except for the 7-year-olds, where the pattern was just the opposite: contrary to our expectations, these children committed more errors in the low memory load condition (see Figure 1). Moreover, this interaction revealed significant differences in low memory load between 7-year-olds and all the other age groups, and between 11-year-olds and all the other ages (all $ps < .001$), but no significant differences were found between 15-year-olds and young adults. On the contrary, in the case of high load condition, significant differences were found among all age groups, including young adults (all $ps < .05$). We also found a significant Age x Suppression interaction, $F(1, 544) = 3.06, p < .03, \eta^2 = .02$, revealing that participants of all age groups committed more intrusions in high suppression condition than in low suppression condition (all $ps < .05$). Moreover, this interaction showed that there were significant differences both under low and high suppression conditions among age groups: 7 year-olds > 11 year-olds > 15 year-olds = young adults.

Furthermore, a significant Age x Load x Suppression interaction was found, $F(3, 544) = 9, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. That is, in low load condition, differences between levels of suppression were significant for 7-year-olds, $t(544) = 9.08, p < .00001, \eta^2 = .13$, 11-year-olds, $t(544) = 6.15, p < .0001, \eta^2 = .07$, and 15-year-olds, $t(544) = 3.87, p < .001, \eta^2 =$

.03, but not for young adults. On the other hand, under high memory load, the effect of suppression was significant for all ages (all $ps < .01$). Under low suppression, differences between high and low memory load were significant for all ages except for 7-year-olds (all $ps < .01$). For high suppression, differences between high and low memory load were significant for all ages (all $ps < .05$) except for 11-year-olds, where the difference was not significant. However, for 7-year-olds, the difference was in the opposite direction from that predicted.

Analysis of types of intrusions

Additionally to this general analysis of intrusions (errors), following De Beni and Palladino (2004), the intrusions were decomposed into same-list intrusions, previous-list intrusions, and inventions. A mixed 4x (3) ANOVA was carried out with age as between-subject factor and type of intrusion as within-subject factor in order to verify whether the type of intrusions committed was different in across ages. Mauchly's test indicated that the assumption of sphericity had been violated for the main effect of type of intrusion, $\chi^2 = 428.83, p < .001$. Therefore, degrees of freedom were corrected using Greenhouse-Geisser corrected degrees of freedom ($\epsilon = .65$ for the main effect of type of intrusions and for the interaction Age x Type of intrusions). This analysis revealed a significant main effect of age, $F(3, 544) = 28.4, p < .001, \eta^2 = .14$. Multiple comparisons indicated that 7-year-olds > 11-year-olds > 15-year-olds = young adults. Moreover, a significant main effect of type of intrusion was obtained, $F(1.29, 703.73) = 333.17, p < .001, \eta^2 = .38$. Contrasts revealed that the proportion of same-list intrusions was higher than previous-list intrusions and inventions (all $ps < .001$). A significant Age x Type of intrusion interaction was also found, $F(3.88, 703.73) = 7.60, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. The analysis of this interaction revealed that the differences between same-list intrusions and previous-list intrusions were significant for all ages (all $ps < .001$). In the same line, differences between same-list intrusions and inventions were also significant for all ages (all $ps < .0001$), but the difference between previous-list intrusions and inventions was not significant for young adults (all $ps < .0001$). Figure 2 shows the proportion of type of

intrusions by age, as well as its developmental trajectories.

[Insert Figure 2]

To analyze the influence of age, memory load and suppression on each intrusion type, a mixed 4x (2 x2) ANOVA was performed with age as between-subject factor and memory load (high and low) and level of suppression (high and low) as within-subject factors.

Bonferroni correction was applied to multiple comparisons.

Same-list intrusions. Same-list intrusions were the recall of irrelevant items for each target list divided by the total number of words to be recalled for each experimental condition.

Table 2 (Panel C) shows the mean proportion of same-list intrusions. ANOVA showed a significant effect of age, $F(3, 544) = 5.99, p < .001, \eta^2 = .03$. Multiple comparisons did not yield differences between 7-year-olds, 11-year-olds, and 15-year-olds. However, there were significant differences of the three groups with young adults (all $ps < .05$). The Age x Load interaction was significant, $F(3, 544) = 60.16, p < .001, \eta^2 = .24$. The analysis of this interaction revealed different patterns of performance in the different age groups. The difference between high and low memory load: a) was significant but contrary to our expectations for 7-year-olds, $F(3, 544) = 121.13, p < .001, \eta^2 = .18$; that is, young children seemed to commit fewer errors in high load condition than in low load condition; b) did not reach standard levels of significance for 11-year-olds; c) was significant in the predicted direction for 15-year-olds, $F(3, 544) = 38.79, p < .001, \eta^2 = .07$, and for young adults, $F(3,$

$544) = 20.53, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$.

Furthermore a significant Age x Suppression interaction was found, $F(3, 544) = 6.25, p < .001, \eta^2 = .03$. The analysis of this interaction showed that all age groups committed more same-list intrusions in the high suppression condition (all $ps < .001$).

Finally, a significant Age x Load x Suppression interaction was found, $F(3, 544) = 8.32, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. Multiple comparisons showed that differences between high and low loads were significant both under low suppression and high suppression conditions in all

ages except for 11-year-olds (all $ps < .05$). In the same line, there were also significant differences between high and low suppression under the high load condition in all ages (all $ps < .05$). However, under low load condition, differences in suppression did not reach standard levels of significance for young adults (all $ps < .05$). All the differences found were in accordance with our predictions except for the 7-year-olds, where the difference between low and high suppression under low load was not in the predicted direction: these young children committed more same-list intrusions in the low load condition than in the high load condition, both under low suppression and high suppression conditions.

Previous-list intrusions. The proportion of previous-list intrusions was the recall of items presented in previous lists divided by the total number of words to be recalled in each experimental condition. Table 2 (Panel D) shows the mean proportion in each experimental condition for all age groups. ANOVA showed a significant effect of age, $F(3, 544) = 50.53$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .22$. Multiple comparisons showed that 7-year-old children $>$ 11-year-olds (4%), $>$ 15-year-olds (2%) = young adults. There was also a significant Age x Load interaction, $F(3, 544) = 6.56$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .04$. The analysis of this interaction revealed that the difference in memory load affected the previous-list intrusions at all ages (all $ps < .001$) except for young adults. Finally, a significant Load x Suppression interaction was found, $F(2, 544) = 4.19$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .008$. The analysis of this interaction revealed that both within low suppression and high suppression conditions, the effect of memory load was significant (all $ps < .001$). The effect of suppression was also significant, but only under high load condition, $F(2, 544) = 3.99$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .007$. This means that previous-list intrusions are controlled by memory load.

Inventions. The proportion of inventions was the recall of words not presented in the experimental lists divided by the total number of words to be recalled for each experimental condition. Table 2 (Panel E) shows the mean proportion of inventions in each experimental condition for each age group. Due to the low number of inventions, these data were not analyzed.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

As stated in the introduction, an additional objective of this study was to test the independence between maintenance and inhibition processes across development. To empirically test these issues, we carried out a PCA with direct oblimin rotation for each age on all the dependent variables with two exceptions: (a) we excluded measures related to inventions at all ages because their correlations with the other dependent variables were too small ($r < .30$); and (b) we also excluded the two measures of correct recall and same-list intrusions in high load/ high suppression condition in 7- and 11-year-olds to avoid confounds due to unexpected effects. Component extraction was made applying parallel analysis (Horn, 1965) on 1000 permutations of the original raw data set. We retained only the components whose original Eigenvalues were greater than the 95th percentile of Eigenvalues from the random data. Factor loadings of .45 and above were used to guide interpretation of factor structure (Tabachnick & Fidell, 1996).

This analysis allowed us to determine how the different variables group in the independent components. Thus, if maintenance and inhibition processes were independent, we should obtain different uncorrelated components for recall and intrusions. And furthermore, if the different types of intrusions reflect different inhibition processes—as suggested by (De Beni & Palladino, 2004)—we should also obtain different uncorrelated components for same-list intrusions and for previous-list intrusions.

7-year-olds. The PCA analysis was conducted on 10 dependent variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure confirmed sample adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .65$. We retained only two components that explained 66.67% of the variance. Table 3 shows component loadings after rotation. Component 1 seems to represent activation/suppression of information in WM. Scores that clustered on this component were related both to maintenance (correct responses) and the suppression of information in WM (same-list intrusions). Component 2 seems to represent the influence of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions). Moreover, and although we allowed components to correlate (through oblimin rotation), correlation between components was close to zero ($r = .06$),

which means that these components are independent for this age group.

[Insert Table 3]

11-year-olds. The PCA analysis was conducted on 10 dependent variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure confirmed sample adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .69$. We retained only two components that explained 65.43% of the variance. Table 3 shows component loadings after rotation. As in the case of 7-year-olds, Component 1 seems to represent activation/suppression of information in WM. Scores that clustered on this component were related both to maintenance (correct responses) and suppression of information in WM (same-list intrusions). Component 2 seems to represent the influence of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions). On the other hand, contrary to the absence of a correlation between components found in the case of 7-year-olds, in 11-year-olds, the correlation between components was .36, which means that the components are not independent.

15-year-olds. The PCA analysis was conducted on 12 dependent variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure confirmed sample adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .62$. We retained only two components that explained 59.21% of the variance. Table 3 shows component loadings after rotation. As in the previous ages, Component 1 seems to represent activation/suppression of information in WM. Scores that clustered on this component were related both to maintenance (correct responses) and suppression of information in WM (same-list intrusions). Component 2 seems to represent the influence of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions). Correlation between components (.32) was similar to that obtained for 11-year-olds.

Young adults. The PCA analysis was conducted on 12 dependent variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure confirmed sample adequacy for the analysis, $KMO = .59$. We retained only one component that explained 37.13% of the variance. Table 3 shows component loadings after rotation. Scores that clustered on this component were mainly related to activation/suppression of information in WM.

Additionally, in order to compare age groups developmentally, component scores

were calculated separately for each one of the groups using weighted average method; we calculated a composite score denominated updating efficiency—the sum of the component scores; that is, of the processes of maintenance/ suppression of information in WM and proactive interference. Then, we carried out different ANOVAs with age as independent factor and updating efficiency composite component as dependent variable. Results showed a significant effect of age for updating efficiency, $F(3, 544) = 274.08, p < .001, \eta^2 = .60$. Post-hoc comparisons showed significant differences between all ages (see Figure 3).

[Insert Figure 3]

Discussion

In the present paper, we aimed to study the development of the updating executive function using De Beni and Palladino's (2004) updating task in an age ranging from 7 years old to young adulthood, as well as to explore the relative independence both between maintenance and inhibition when updating information, and among various inhibition processes in the different age groups.

We will discuss the results obtained in different sections to better analyze all the different aspects that they imply.

Factors affecting updating information in WM

Our results showed that memory performance in the updating task was affected not only by age, but also by maintenance and suppression demands.

Maintenance demands (WM load) affects both the percentage of recall of critical items (memory performance) and the percentage of errors (intrusions) and also, and importantly, this effect varies across development. That is, the cost of memory load on recall—the difference in recall between high load and low load conditions—becomes lower as age increases until the age of 15, that is, as age increases, high memory load becomes less demanding except for the 7-year-old group, where an absence of costs of high memory load was found. This result could be due to the high proportion of missing answers observed in these young children, maybe as a consequence of low WMC. These results, together with the relation found between memory load and suppression, suggest that memory performance was

dominated by the amount of information that should be kept in WM. This pattern of results reminds one of those obtained by De Beni and Palladino (2004) with older individuals and those of Macizo, Bajo, & Soriano (2006), who found a clear relationship between WM span and performance in De Beni and Palladino's updating task. However, our results contradict those of Lechuga et al. (2006), which seemed to find that performance in this task was driven by inhibitory demands.

Another important result that abounds in this aspect was the relation found between age, memory load, and suppression. The lack of differences in memory performance as a function of inhibitory demands under both low and high memory load in young adults suggested that inhibition is not hard for adults. The opposite is true for the rest of age groups—including 15-year-olds—where significant differences between high and low inhibitory demands were found mainly under low memory demands. In the high memory load conditions, differences between inhibitory demands become significant only as of 15 years of age, which presumably coincides with increments in WMC. Difficulties in inhibition were also replicated in errors that reflect inefficient mechanisms of suppression of information in WM (same-list intrusions) but in this case, difficulties in inhibition were only found under high memory demands, which could be indicating—according to executive attention theory—that efficient inhibition also demands attentional resources. These results are similar to those obtained by Davidson, Amso, Anderson, and Diamond (2006) with age spectrum ranging from 4 to 45 years old in tasks that tax both WM (maintenance of rules) and inhibition (prepotent response inhibition) in a switching context.

Taken together, the fact that memory performance was controlled by memory load manipulation (not by inhibitory demands) and the lack of differences found in memory performance as a function of inhibitory demands, our data seem to support the executive attention theory (Engle, 2002), which underlines that WMC is what drives inhibitory processes in WM. That is, inhibition is an effortful resource-dependent process that can be impaired when not enough attentional resources are available (Engle, Conway, Tuholski, & Shisler, 1995), in our case, under high memory load conditions. It is important to underline

this, because Lustig, Hasher, and Zacks (2007) argued that much of the work on high-span versus low-span young adults that supports executive attentional theory can also be understood in terms of differences in inhibitory functions. We think that this explanation is not suitable for the present data because, unlike the WM complex span task, in the updating WM task used in our study, load and inhibition are manipulated independently. *Development of inhibitory mechanisms*

Our results showed that younger participants committed more errors than the older ones (7-year-olds committed twice as many errors as young adults). The analysis of these errors as a function of age showed that development of inhibitory mechanisms progresses from childhood to young adulthood. These data corroborate results found with different experimental paradigms reporting a developmental increase in inhibitory efficiency (see Harnishfeger & Bjorklund, 1993; Dempster & Corkill, 1999); results found with this task by Lechuga et al. (2006); and are also in the same line as neurodevelopmental studies that underline the relation of the development of inhibitory mechanisms with maturation of the prefrontal cortex (Fuster, 1997).

Importantly, however, our results showed that the development of the different inhibitory mechanisms do not progress in the same way. All the age groups committed more errors that depend on inefficient suppression mechanisms operating in WM (same-list intrusions) compared to errors related to the control of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions), especially 15-year-olds and young adults. These results are similar to those obtained by De Beni and Palladino (2004) and Lechuga et al. (2006) in aging and in development, respectively, both using a similar updating task. However, the percentage of errors related to the control of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions) was significantly higher at the age of 7. This means that the inhibition difficulties observed in this age group could reflect a general inhibitory deficit related both to a difficulty suppressing irrelevant information in WM and to inhibiting information from LTM, results that are similar to those obtained by Harnishfeger and Bjorklund (1993) or Lechuga et al. (2006) with younger children and by De Beni and Palladino (2004) with old adults.

Additionally, our results also show different developmental trajectories in inhibitory mechanisms. Globally, errors more closely related to inhibition—which depends on inefficient suppression mechanisms that operate in WM (same-list intrusions)—remained stable during childhood and adolescence and did not decrease until young adulthood. On the contrary, errors that depend on mechanisms of control of proactive interference (previous-list intrusions) showed a continuous and progressive decrement until 15 years of age. These different developmental patterns observed of suppression of information in WM and control and blocking of information from LTM suggest that the inhibitory mechanism that prevents interference from LTM develops earlier and faster than those responsible for suppression of information in WM.

On the one hand, these results pointed to the dissociation between inhibitory processes—also corroborated by the results of principal component analysis in 7-, 11-, and 15-year-olds—but also to the fact that both processes are closely related. In fact, for these three age groups, the two different components obtained—maintenance/suppression of information in WM and resistance to proactive interference—were completely independent at the age of 7, but as development advanced, they became progressively more related (correlations of .36 and .32, respectively for 11- and 15-year-olds) until becoming completely indistinguishable in young adults. These results apparently contradict those obtained by some authors who claim the differentiation of inhibitory functions with age, especially the results of Brydges (Brydges et al., 2012; Brydges, Anderson, Reid & Fox, 2013; Brydges, Fox, Reid & Anderson 2014), who found both behavioral and neurocognitive evidence for the dissociability of interference suppression (resisting interference from distracting stimuli) and response inhibition (inhibition of prepotent automatic responses) across development. However, the updating WM task used in our study taps a different kind of inhibitory processes—cognitive inhibition processes—, whose correlation with Response-Distractor Inhibition (measured by Brydges and colleagues) was close to zero in adults (Friedman & Miyake, 2004). Unfortunately, to our knowledge, there are as yet no studies addressing this topic in children and adolescents.

However, the lack of differentiation between maintenance/suppression of information in WM and resistance to proactive interference found in our adult participants is consistent with the neurocognitive evidence pointing to the same neural systems underlying both WM and resolution of interference in adults (Bunge, Ochsner, Desmond, Glover, & Gabrieli, 2001; Burgess, Gray, Conway, & Braver, 2011; Mecklinger, Weber, Gunter, & Engle, 2003; Hester, Murphy & Garavan, 2004).

Globally, inhibitory results corroborate the thesis of Friedman and Miyake (2004), which states that inhibition is not a unitary construct, as well as the work of some other authors such as Dempster and Corkill (1999), Harnishfeger (1995), and Nigg (2000).

However, what our results importantly and originally point out is that the relationship among inhibitory mechanisms could change across development, a topic that requires deeper future research.

Developmental trajectories in the updating executive function

According to our predictions and to previous results obtained with this task (De Beni & Palladino, 2004; Lechuga et al., 2006; Palladino et al., 2001), our results showed that there is an improvement of memory performance as age increases together with an upgrading of inhibitory process efficiency. However, developmental trajectories of memory performance and inhibition are somewhat different. Whereas in memory performance, a progressive increment was observed until the age of 15 followed by stabilization, inhibitory efficiency – measured as the proportion of intrusions – increased until young adulthood.

With regard to the developmental trajectory in memory performance, our results corroborated those obtained by other authors (Conklin et al., 2007; de Abreu, Conway, & Gathercole, 2010; Gathercole et al., 2004; Gathercole et al., 2008; Huizinga et al., 2006) who reported WM increments from childhood into adolescence with complex span tasks, but seemed to contradict those obtained by Lechuga et al. (2006) who obtained developmental differences both in the amount of information recalled and in inhibition, but only until age 11.

Our results neither corroborate those of Luciana et al. (2005) nor those of Luna et al. (2004), or some results of Conklin et al. (2007), who found that WM continues to develop until age 16-17 years and remains stable around 18-20 years with complex WM tasks that require self-organization and with backward digit span task.

However, the PCA carried out could shed some light on the development of the updating executive function after adolescence. The analysis conducted showed that updating information in WM tapped by this task implies several inseparable components or subprocesses: active maintenance /suppression of information in WM on the one hand, and control of proactive interference on the other hand. Thus, we think that the developmental trajectory of the updating process will be best understood if maintenance and inhibition processes are considered conjointly—as our PCA showed— than if we study the development of memory performance and inhibition separately, as has been done before by other cited studies. When we did this, developmental trajectories showed that maintenance/inhibition component continues to develop far beyond adolescence (see Figure 3) in agreement with other developmental studies (Conklin et al., 2007; Crone et al., 2006; Luciana et al., 2005; Luna et al., 2004) using complex span tasks.

Finally, a very interesting result is that the first component obtained in PCA (maintenance/inhibition of information in WM) explained a similar percentage of variance in 7-, 11-, and 15-year-olds (48%, 49%, and 46%, respectively) and a lower percentage in young adults (37%). The second component (proactive interference) explained a smaller amount of variance in all ages, but its developmental differences were more pronounced (24%, 17%, and 13%, for 7-, 11- and 15-year-olds, respectively). Thus, our results could be also indicate that proactive interference is the factor responsible for the updating variation observed in development, as Dempster (1981) also stated. These results could be explained by the limited resources models of cognitive development that postulate that the limited pool of mental resources (mental capacity) available both for storing information and for cognitive processing does not increase across development. However, what changes with age is the efficiency in the execution of cognitive processes, which can be conceptualized as the speed

of activation/suppression of information (Bjorklund & Harnishfeger, 1990; Case, Kurland, & Goldberg, 1982; Harnishfeger, 1995).

These results also indicate that information updating in the WM requires both the maintenance of relevant information and the inhibition of irrelevant information, which is consistent with the conceptual distinctions made about the underlying updating processes (e.g., Kessler & Meiran, 2008; Kessler & Oberauer, 2014). These authors specifically asserted the need to postulate a mechanism of active removal to minimize interference from irrelevant information, and consequently, allowing more efficient WM processing (Ecker, Oberauer, & Lewandowsky, 2014). Our results also corroborate both the findings of Friedman and Miyake (2004) in adults, indicating that the inhibitory mechanisms responsible for interference of previously relevant information were linked to WM performance; and also the findings of other authors who linked WM capacity to executive attention (e.g., Bunting, 2006; Burgess et al., 2011; Engle, 2002; Kane & Engle, 2000), emphasizing that WM capacity does not directly concern the capacity of remembering items of information, but using attention to maintain or suppress information and to avoid distraction. Moreover, our results are congruent with the neural findings of Bunge et al. (2001) or Mecklinger et al. (2003), who reported the close relationship between neural systems activated in WM and those implied in interference control in adulthood.

Our results also indicate that information updating in the WM requires both the maintenance of relevant information and the inhibition of irrelevant information, which is consistent with the conceptual distinctions made about the underlying updating processes (e.g., Kessler & Meiran, 2008; Kessler & Oberauer, 2014) and with the need to postulate a mechanism of active removal to minimize interference from irrelevant information, thus allowing more efficient WM processing (Ecker, Oberauer, & Lewandowsky, 2014). They are, then, compatible with the dual-mode theories (Kessler & Oberauer, 2014) of WM that proposed two different operation modes: (a) a default maintenance mode, which enables WM to keep information intact and resistant to the influence of other inputs and provides stability to the memory system and (b) an updating mode in charge of modification of representations in

memory, which provides flexibility. According to these theories, selective updating of WM contents entails switching between maintenance and up- dating modes of WM, and these switches have a time cost, which is responsible for the variability in WM.

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Table 1. Composition of the lists as a function of the experimental conditions

Low load/low suppression (5 Lists)	Low load/high suppression (5 Lists)	High load/low suppression (5 Lists)	High load/high suppression (5 Lists)
3 Relevant items	3 Relevant items	5 Relevant items	5 Relevant items
2 Irrelevant items	5 Irrelevant items	2 Irrelevant items	5 Irrelevant items
7 Filler items	4 Filler items	5 Filler items	2 Filler items

Table 2. Mean proportion (and standard deviations) of correct answers and errors

Panel A. Recall of critical words					
Age	Low load		High load		Overall
	Low suppression	High suppression	Low suppression	High suppression	
7 years	.71 (.19)	.64 (.22)	.53 (.16)	.55 (.17)	.61
11 years	.83 (.19)	.77 (.21)	.64 (.14)	.64 (.16)	.72
15 years	.91 (.11)	.88 (.14)	.78 (.12)	.76 (.13)	.83
Young adults	.92 (.10)	.92 (.09)	.81 (.11)	.80 (.13)	.86
Overall	.84 (.18)	.80 (.21)	.69 (.18)	.69 (.18)	.76
Panel B. Intrusions					
7 years	.21 (.17)	.30 (.20)	.21 (.17)	.24 (.17)	.24
11 years	.13 (.17)	.19 (.20)	.17 (.13)	.21 (.16)	.18
15 years	.08 (.10)	.12 (.14)	.15 (.11)	.19 (.13)	.14
Young adults	.06 (.09)	.08 (.09)	.11 (.08)	.15 (.11)	.10
Overall	.13 (.15)	.18 (.19)	.17 (.14)	.20 (.15)	.17
Panel C. Same-list intrusions					
7 years	.12 (.14)	.24 (.18)	.07 (.08)	.10 (.10)	.13
11 years	.10 (.15)	.16 (.18)	.10 (.09)	.15 (.13)	.13
15 years	.06 (.09)	.10 (.12)	.10 (.08)	.16 (.12)	.11
Young adults	.05 (.08)	.07 (.09)	.08 (.07)	.12 (.10)	.08
Overall	.09 (.13)	.14 (.16)	.09 (.08)	.13 (.12)	.11
Panel D. Previous-lists intrusions					
7 years	.06 (.09)	.06 (.08)	.10 (.11)	.09 (.10)	.08
11 years	.02 (.05)	.03 (.06)	.07 (.08)	.06 (.06)	.04
15 years	.01 (.03)	.01 (.03)	.04 (.05)	.03 (.04)	.02
Young adults	.01 (.02)	.01 (.02)	.01 (.03)	.02 (.03)	.01
Overall	.03 (.06)	.03 (.06)	.06 (.08)	.05 (.07)	.05
Panel E. Inventions					
7 years	.02 (.05)	.02 (.04)	.05 (.10)	.05 (.08)	.04
11 years	.01 (.02)	.00 (.02)	.00 (.02)	.01 (.02)	.01
15 years	.00 (.02)	.00 (.01)	.00 (.01)	.01 (.02)	.01
Young adults	.00 (.02)	.00 (.01)	.00 (.01)	.01 (.02)	.01
Overall	.01 (.03)	.01 (.08)	.02 (.03)	.02 (.05)	.01

Table 3. Summary of PCA

	7		11		15		Young adults
	Components		Components		Components		Components
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1
Ll-Ls- previous-list- intrusions	.12	.72	.26	.39	.19	.53	.46
Ll-Hs- previous-list- intrusions	.16	.74	.07	.69	.31	.51	.35
Hl-Ls- previous-list- intrusions	-.14	.82	-.08	.87	.20	.75	.18
Hl-Hs- previous-list- intrusions	-.14	.85	-.08	.85	.13	.73	.38
Ll-Ls-correct-answers	-.84	-.12	-.91	-.01	-.82	-.32	-.77
Ll-Hs-correct-answers	-.84	-.14	-.90	-.06	-.84	-.31	-.68
Hl-Ls-correct-answers	-.73	.00	-.63	-.22	-.73	-.64	-.70
Hl-Hs-correct-answers					-.82	-.36	-.84
Ll-Ls- same-list- intrusions	.86	-.14	.91	-.06	.83	.16	.70
Ll-Hs- same-list- intrusions	.84	-.08	.96	-.12	.84	.21	.64
Hl-Ls- same-list- intrusions	.82	-.01	.68	-.01	.75	.31	.52
Hl-Hs- same-list- intrusions					.80	.12	.69
Eigenvalues	4.17	2.50	4.85	1.69	5.25	1.58	4.45
% of variance	41.67	24.99	48.51	16.92	46.04	13.17	37.13

Factor loadings over .45 appear in bold. Ll: low load, Hl: high load, Ls: low suppression, Hs: high suppression.

Figure 1. Proportion of recall and intrusions as a function of age and experimental condition.

Vertical lines depict standard errors of the means.

Figure 3. Updating efficiency developmental trajectories. Vertical lines depict standard errors of the means.

